

CLASSIFICATION, SYSTEM AND TERMS OF SPORT WRESTLING METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Dividing different methods of struggle according to their common characteristics (classifications) allows professionals to develop theoretical and practical knowledge about the science and at the same time helps to identify gaps in this knowledge. In wrestling, the athlete's technical movements are different and different from other sports due to their diversity. This article deals with the issues of classification, system and basic terminology of kurash struggle methods. Provides valuable recommendations on learning techniques and the use of kurash terminology.

In wrestling, the athlete's technical movements are different and different from other sports due to their diversity. The classification, system and terminology of wrestling techniques have been developed to regulate the technical actions of the wrestler and to create an opportunity for communication between specialists in this field. Classification is a system of interdependent concepts (classes, objects, events) in a particular field of knowledge. The classification is based on the common characteristics of the objects and the legal relationship between them. Classification helps to behave correctly in different objects and is a source of knowledge about them.

Dividing different methods of struggle according to their common characteristics (classifications) allows professionals to develop theoretical and practical knowledge of the science, and at the same time helps to identify gaps in this knowledge. The internal connections between the methods of struggle are considered on the basis of systematization. Systematization is the process of putting wrestling techniques into a system, placing them in a certain order, defining a certain sequence. [1]

In systematization, in contrast to classification (because the objects considered during it belong to this or that subdivision, taking into account their similarity and interdependence), objects are compared with each other to determine their sequence. The systematization reveals the possibilities of this classification scheme, pointing out its shortcomings. [2]

The task of classifying and systematizing sports wrestling is to reflect the essence of wrestling. Classification and systematization cannot be done without prior work on defining the concepts (throwing, transferring, demolishing, overturning, etc.). A well-structured

classification is the basis for creating science-based terms. Wrestling terminology is a set of terms used by specialists in their scientific and pedagogical work.

Terminology, which is based on the classification and systematization of many disciplines, provides information about the essence of science and can be purposefully improved. Such terminology is called science-based terminology. Thus, when thinking about classification, systematization, and terminology, one can see the sequence of work on classification in them, paying attention to the fact that they are listed in this order. That is, first a classification is performed, as a result of which a certain system is formed, and then on its basis all the methods of struggle are given scientifically based names (terms). Different types of wrestling have common laws (according to AP Kuptsov) and they are: The fight involves two athletes, each of whom wins over his opponent using methods or counter-methods. Thus, in each individual moment of the fight, there is a wrestler who is attacking and being attacked, that is, a wrestler who is performing a method or combination, and a wrestler who is performing a method and a combination (a wrestler who performs a counter-attack is called a counter-attacker). One of the main tasks of every wrestler movement activity is to maintain the chosen position. The task of the attacking wrestler is to unbalance the opponent to change his position relative to the carpet. In this case, the position of the wrestlers in relation to each other may vary. Changing the position of the rug is facilitated by the fact that the wrestlers use the force of gravity directed at the rug. [3]

Giving the required force to a given given point of the opponent's body (i.e., generating moments of force, creating a pair of forces, using gravitational forces and moments of inertia) forms the biomechanical basis of each method. The method allows you to win by force and consists of several parts: preparatory movement, catch, main movement, attack and closing situations. Each method can be modified and complicated depending on the dynamic situation as well as the characteristics of the competitor. Each method has its own rhythm-speed characteristics. It can be changed in one or another situation of the competition or in the whole competition. The location of each method is limited by the size of the wrestling mat. [4] The content of the different types of wrestling has a common basis and is classified according to the same characteristics, although the actions of wrestlers in each type of wrestling separately have their own characteristics. On this basis, AP Kuptsov developed a single classification and system of wrestling techniques (Table 1). In this case, the specific features of each species are fully preserved, just as the characteristics of this species are preserved.

Table 1 Unified classification scheme of basic techniques in wrestling (revised by AP Kuptsov)

1st degree Level 2 Level 3 Level 4

Classes

Small classes

Groups

Small groups

Methods of standing

Transfers

Shaking, passing under the arm, spinning, squatting Generating options for methods that can be performed with different interceptions in different directions and movement with arms and legs performed differently. Overturn With a blow, turn Drops Raise the front, bend the back, lift the shoulder (turn), bend back, turn, with a blow, bend, sit. Methods on the ground

floor Conversions Rolling, running, crossing, rolling, bending back, rolling over, writing. Drops Leaning forward, raising from the back, leaning back, rounding. Hold on From the side, from the side of the head, from the side of the foot, from above, transversely. Get to the top Squeeze (squeeze), squeeze, twist (knot). Sink, run away (forward, backward), take a pass. It hurts Choking Pull and squeeze. The following tasks are set in the development of a single classification and system of basic methods of wrestling techniques:

- reflecting its essence, revealing the diversity and complexity of the interrelationships between the technical movements of wrestling;
- to reflect what is happening on the carpet without comparing the type of wrestling;
- help to determine the commonality for all types of wrestling;
- to preserve the peculiarities of each type of wrestling;
- to create an opportunity for each type of wrestling to master the best techniques from other types (including national wrestling);
- Classification of basic techniques in "school performance";
- to develop technical concepts and definitions common to all types of wrestling and to help create a terminology based on general principles of each type. [5]

The main feature of a single classification and systematization of wrestling is that all its levels are a step-by-step expression of the technique of any sport (including national) wrestling and help to regulate a large number of elements.

The first level - the classes - shows how the struggle is being waged. The technical movements of wrestling are performed both standing and on the ground.

The second level - the subclasses - shows what is being done in the fight (throwing, passing, overthrowing, etc.). The third level - groups - shows how the method, i.e. the types of possible basic actions of the attacking wrestlers while performing the methods, is performed. For example, throws can be bent forward, bent backwards, turned, and so on. is performed. The fourth level - small groups - shows possible hand-holding, leg movements, and other features of the performance of the methods, i.e., the variability of the methods within the group itself. [6]

Using such a structure of the system, it is possible to name all the methods and list them in the same order, depending on the increasing complexity of execution. This is also a system. Any technical action that can be performed on the carpet is included in this classification table. The first step in forming the name of the methods, i.e. standing or performing on the ground, is not indicated. This is implied, or will be further explained in these cases if it is a question of methods (e.g., throws) available both on the upright and on the ground. The name of each method begins to form from the second level, i.e. the subclass. From each complete naming of the methods, there should be three sections corresponding to three levels of classification, thus indicating the place of this method in the general system. To describe the methods, you need to know: What was done on the carpet (throwing, moving, overturning, etc.), i.e. which subgroup the method belongs to (level 2).

How the method was performed (leaning back, leaning forward), i.e. which group the method describes describing the main movement of the attacking wrestler (level 3).

How the method was performed with capture and other features, i.e. what variant of the method is envisaged in this case (level 4).

For example, grab the arms and torso (level 4) and bend back (level 3) and throw (level 2).

In short, the terminology of sports wrestling, developed on the basis of a single classification on a single methodology, is of great importance for the entire scientific-methodical and sports-pedagogical activity of specialists.

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